

POPE FRANCIS' APPROACH TO EXISTENTIAL PERIPHERIES Marginalized and Impoverished as Theological and Ecclesial Locus

Dr. Savio VAZ SAC

The author <savio vaz@gmx.de> is a Pallottine Priest. He has done his doctorate in Moral theology in the University of Bonn and the postdoctoral thesis in the University of Freiburg, Germany. Presently he is teaching Moral Theology in Vinzenz Pallotti University in Vallendar, Germany.

Abstract: Preferential option for the poor has become a constituent of the Catholic Social Teaching. Pope Francis was called the “Pope of the peripheries.” This title highlights his authentic witness to the Gospel; the Church is called to live the joy of the Gospel, especially with the poor and the needy. She is sent to the marginalized, sick, and vulnerable. This article tries to trace the theological and ethical roots of his teaching and the relevance of the evangelization today.

Keywords: Pope Francis, Existential Peripheries, Poor, Healthcare, Right to Health, Poor Church, Evangelization, Pact of the Catacombs.

INTRODUCTION

In view of increasing threats to human health and life, triggered by global environmental, climatic changes and socio-economic differences, there is a growing worldwide concern not only for the pathetic condition of the poor and marginalized but also for the primary health care (PHC). Economically and socially underprivileged and vulnerable people have limited access to healthcare. Low socio-economic status and poverty exacerbate health disparities within the society and various socio-ethnic groups. The insurmountable difficulties and inabilities faced by patients

in poverty make the access to convalescence almost impossible.¹ In this connection, experts speak about the social determinants of health or social determinants of health inequalities.² They are the conditions in the environments where people are born, live, work, learn, play, and worship. All these aspects influence health and drive widening and deepening health inequalities. Poor and poverty are not the same. We have to differentiate and ask ourselves who are the “poor” today and their standing. To the poor belong also the socially excluded groups. Gender inequality plays negative role in healthcare. Groups such as women, girls, ethnic, religious groups, refugees, mentally or physically disabled, people with chronic diseases like HIV/AIDS have limited accessibility to healthcare. There are several other people who are excluded because of their caste, cultural beliefs, language, or geographical remoteness. Social determinants are again influenced by structural determinants, which are root causes of health disparities.

Simultaneously, healthcare costs are rapidly increasing all over the world. Rising healthcare expenses bring many affected persons and families on the brink of financial ruin and existential fears. Due to the substantial loss of regular income, families are forced to sell their assets in order to maintain their household expenses.³ Many people cannot afford medical care and the basic health insurance. Our country Despite being one of the fastest growing world’s major economies, a substantial number of India’s citizens, especially the lower income groups, struggle with healthcare affordability. Health systems too face financial crunch and are forced to

¹ OECD (WHO), *Poverty and Health* (Paris, 2003), 19-27.

² Michael Marmot, “Social Determinants of Health,” *The Lancet* 365 (2005): 1099-1104.

³ Owen O’Donnell, “Health and Health System Effects on Poverty: A Narrative Review of Global Evidence,” *Health Policy* 142 (2024): 105018, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0168851024000289> (accessed on 20.05.2025).

decrease medical stations and facilities. Contemporary healthcare challenges are not only because of an ever-ageing population, but also because of the rising cases of chronic illnesses and other medical possibilities of operation and treatments.

Healthcare systems worldwide are in crisis. In times of economic crisis, governments are forced to adopt measures of austerity, which have an impact on health system. The modern scientific medicine and the financial corporatization of medical practice threaten to wipe out the good old practice of relational and philanthropic dimension of medicine. In view of healthcare crisis facing countries and underprivileged people, United Nations Organization (UNO) has called world community to return to the Declaration of Alma-Ata International Conference on Primary Health Care, as the key solution to attaining and protecting health for all. The 1978 Alma-Ata Declaration, which formulated a vision for the future, reaffirms

that health, which is a state of complete physical, mental and social wellbeing, and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity, is a fundamental human right and that the attainment of the highest possible level of health is a most important world-wide social goal whose realization requires the action of many other social and economic sectors in addition to the health sector.⁴

National governments were urged to take measures for ensuring primary health care for all by the year 2000.

1. IS THERE A SO-CALLED RIGHT TO HEATH OR HEALTHCARE?

From a mere ethical norm, is the right to health incorporated in national and international law? A number of international treaties and declarations use the language of rights to health

⁴ International Conference on Primary Health Care, Alma-Ata, USSR, 6-12 September 1978, Art. 1. https://cdn.who.int/media/docs/default-source/documents/almaata-declaration-en.pdf?sfvrsn=7b3c2167_2 (accessed on 20.05.2025).

issues.⁵ The “right to health” is older than the “right to healthcare.” The Preamble of the Constitution of the World Health Organization (WHO, 1946) articulates the right to health, stating that “the enjoyment of the highest attainable standard of health is one of the fundamental rights of every human being.” The international law acknowledges the individual’s right to health. The Article 25 of the United Nations’s Declaration of Human Rights (1948) states,

Everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and of his family, including food, clothing, housing and medical care and necessary social services, and the right to security in the event of unemployment, sickness, disability, widowhood, old age or other lack of livelihood in circumstances beyond his control.⁶

The UNO Convention on the Right of Persons with Disability, 2006, recognizes the right of persons with disability to the highest attainment standard of health without any restrictions or discrimination. The European Charter of Fundamental Rights speaks in Art. 35:

Everyone has the right of access to preventive health care and the right to benefit from medical treatment under the conditions established by national laws and practices. A high level of human health protection shall be ensured in the definition and implementation of all Union policies and activities.⁷

The right to health is an inclusive right. Good health is the result of many other connecting factors such as good air, water, food, freedom from noise, dust pollution, including mental and spiritual health.⁸

⁵ Virginia A. Leary, “The Right to Health in International Human Rights Law,” *Health and Human Rights* 1 (1994): 24-56.

⁶ International Conference on Primary Health Care, Art. 25/1.

⁷ EU-Charter, IV Solidarity, Art. 35.

⁸ Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, *The Right to Health* (Geneva, Fact Sheet No. 31).

2. THE RIGHT TO HEALTHCARE AND HEALTH BENEFITS FOR ALL?

Human rights include the right to healthcare and access to it.⁹ The Universal Human Rights try to uphold the individual rights and individuals' wellbeing through healthcare system. However, what is the right to health or healthcare, "what exactly individuals are entitled to on the basis of a right to health and what the ensuing obligations are on the part of State."¹⁰

The responsibility of the national governments is to ensure that the rights of the individuals are protected against selection and discrimination. The Human Rights Declaration uses categories like availability, accessibility, acceptability, and quality regarding healthcare offers. *Availability* means that the provision of functioning healthcare facilities and medical care for the sick and the needy. It varies from having safe drinking water to basic conditions like sanitation and essential medicines. The *accessibility* to medical healthcare means that all have open access to medical treatment without any discrimination and reservation. Marginalized and minorities should have the equal access to medical facilities. All people should have access to information. *Acceptability* means here that the medical facilities and medical care offered to the people must be carried out in accordance with the principles of medical ethics with the solemn aim to improve the health of the affected persons.¹¹

Can the healthcare be offered to every citizen, irrespective of their economic and social status?¹² From

⁹ Anja Rudiger, "Human Rights and the Political Economy of Universal Health Care: Designing Equitable Financing," *Health and Human Rights Journal* 18 (2016): 67-78.

¹⁰ Brigit C. A. Toebes, *The Right to Health as a Human Right in International Law* (Amsterdam: Hart-Intersentia, 1999), 25.

¹¹ Michael Krennerich, "The Human Right to Health. Fundamentals of a Complex Right," in *Health Care as a Human Right Issue: Normative Profile, Conflicts and Implementation*, ed. S. Klotz, et al. (Bielefeld: Transcript, 2017), 23-54.

¹² Jacob Nielsen Arendt, "The Demand for Health Care by the Poor under universal Health Care Coverage," *Journal of Human Capital* 6 (2012): 316-335.

the present situation, we notice that the modern medicine and its offers remain limited only to certain sections of the society. Poor and downtrodden citizens often do not have the privilege of occupying a bed in the intensive care unit of a hospital. The question of healthcare cost and affordability can harm especially socially weak individuals and their families, and deteriorate their health. The States carry the full responsibility and are called upon to adopt positive measures to ensure that no persons or groups become victims of discrimination and exclusion.

Further, the nature and scope of such international rights are still contested; they are interpreted differently in different countries; hence, the recognition of such rights remains contentious.¹³ Some interpret the right to health as not implied legal right to health, while others highlight the demand for the social determinants of health. They are unable to define the proper content of an international right to health.

Even international human rights law documents that highlight the importance of health care often end up collapsing the distinction between health care and social determinants of health in a way that supports reading the right to health as fundamentally concerned with the social determinants.¹⁴

There is a difference between right to healthcare and the recognition of a certain social determinant of healthcare. Despite the numerous international treaties and declaration on human rights and right to health, there exists no single, common and universally agreed definition of a human right approach, let alone its application to the right to health.¹⁵ No discipline can claim the sole ownership of the terms ‘human rights,’ ‘right to health,’ or ‘rights-based approach.’ “These terms may be used differently by various stakeholders,

¹³ Michael Da Silva, “The International Right to Health Care: A Legal and Moral Defence,” *Michigan Journal of International Law* 39 (2018): 343-384.

¹⁴ *Ibid.*, 349.

¹⁵ David Patterson, “Human Rights-Based Approaches and the Right to Health: A Systematic Literature Review,” *Journal of Human Rights Practice* 16 (2024): 603-623.

including from the legal, health and development domains. Scholars and advocates should therefore be encouraged to state their perspectives and to define their terms."¹⁶

The right to health is not a standalone right, but includes many claims. Healthcare guarantees are defined in terms of rights and laws in order to protect the dignity of every person and to disdain discrimination of every kind. The right to healthcare or health legislation cannot alone safeguard the health benefits for the poor and vulnerable. It is true that social conditions could be of help to a certain extent. To achieve the right to health, health legislations should tackle a wide variety of barriers that hinder poor patients from having access to healthcare facilities.

The Declaration of the human rights and the national ratification of the international law try to protect the life and dignity of each person, irrespective of her or his socio-economic or ethnic background. The right to life and the right to personal integrity involve automatically the right to respect private life and the right to health. In respecting the human rights, the States have the obligation to obtain informed consent for any medical treatment.¹⁷ Health equity is a social justice in matters of health. The human rights cannot alone fight against the fate of the poor and vulnerable. There must be a conceptual and spiritual motivation to develop solidarity with them. How can Christian healthcare ethics bring change into the perception of the moral virtue of justice and the dignity of human person?

3. CHRISTIANITY & HEALTHCARE: THE ETHICS OF DIVINE MERCY

No other world religion has given such a high priority to the poor, outcasts, sick, and dying as the Christianity. The Gospel message of Jesus was a major catalyst in changing

¹⁶ Ibid., 620.

¹⁷ David N. Weisstub and Guillermo Diaz Pintos, *Autonomy and Human Rights in Health care: An International Perspective* (Dordrecht: Springer, 2008).

and developing healthcare in the world. It has played and continues to play a significant role in the foundation of the modern healthcare system. The New Testament presents Jesus as the Great Physician who not only restored people to spiritual and psychological wellbeing but also cured their physical ailments. Christian understanding of philanthropy was motivated and framed by Christ-like agapeic service towards the lowly, unlike the pagan Greco-Roman cultures. Gary Ferngren notes,

Philanthropy among the Greeks did not take the form of private charity or of a personal concern for those in need, such as orphans, widows, or the sick. There was no religious or ethical impulse for almsgiving; ... In contrast with the emphasis in Judaism on God as particularly concerned for the welfare of the poor, the Greek and Roman gods showed little pity on them; indeed, they showed greater regard for the powerful who could offer them sacrifices.¹⁸

The Christian understanding of God's mercy does not exclude anyone from God and his maternal and paternal care for them. The dignity of each human person is valuable in the eyes of God and has tangible consequence for Christian ethics. David Bentley Hart writes, "Christian teaching from the first placed charity at the centre of the spiritual life as no pagan cult ever had, and raised the care of widows, orphans, the sick, the imprisoned and the poor to the level of the highest of religious obligations."¹⁹

The privileged place given to fellow human beings and especially to the poor and "the least" originates from the basic theological understanding of human beings. Unlike the pagan understanding of human being,²⁰ the intrinsic human worth is bestowed by God gratuitously, irrespective

¹⁸ Gary B. Ferngren, *Medicine and Health Care in Early Christianity* (Baltimore: John Hopkins University Press, 2009), 87.

¹⁹ David Bentley Hart, *Atheist Delusions: The Christian Revolution and Its Fashionable Enemies* (New Haven – London: Yale University Press, 2009), 164.

²⁰ Ferngren, *Medicine and Health Care*, 95.

of one's socio-economic or political position. The biblical anthropology states that human person is created in the image and likeness of God (Gen 1:26-27). The New Testament too delves deeply into the nature and identity of human person as envisioned by God. Jesus lived consequently such theological anthropology. The Exodus event marks the iconic intervention of God as the deliverer of the people of Israel. Yahweh is the first liberator, who rescues Israel out of its bondage. We find in the book of Exodus the preference of God for Israel. The Lord said,

I have indeed seen the misery of my people in Egypt. I have heard them crying out because of their slave drivers, and I am concerned about their suffering. So, I have come down to rescue them from the hand of the Egyptians and to bring them up out of that land into a good and spacious land, a land flowing with milk and honey—the home of the Canaanites, Hittites, Amorites, Perizzites, Hivites and Jebusites (Ex 3:7-8).

God takes the side of the oppressed and not of the strong. He hears the cry of the poor (Ps 34:6).

God's love and concern is for everyone, but especially for the poor and vulnerable. Jesus preached the option for the poor in the Gospel. He is the model of Christian agape and service as he reiterates his identification with the downtrodden, "Whatever you do to the least of these, you do to me" (Mt 25:40). The agapeic love of Jesus serves as an example to identify ourselves with the pain and suffering of others. Christians understood the meaning of serving the poor and destitute. Serving the poor meant following Christ. "The deepest meaning of the commitment to the poor is the encounter with Christ."²¹ Jesus the Great Physician sought holistic health for the ill and disabled. He healed their mind, body, and soul so that they may flourish and practice the love of God and the neighbour.

²¹ Gustavo Gutiérrez, "The Option for the Poor Arises from Faith in Christ," *Theological Studies* 70 (2009): 320.

One of the central objectives of the human rights declaration is that it appeals against discrimination and fights for equality of all persons. Just as all are equal before God, so the law must protect individuals from injustice and arbitrariness. Human rights are instruments in the field of healthcare whereby its provisions protect the autonomy of the patients from misuse.²² The principle of autonomy can be explained as follows:

[I]t means self-rule not rule of others. Autonomous refusal of treatment is self-rule. Autonomous request for treatment seeks and requires autonomous consent from the person requested who may justifiably decline consent. The second reminder is that autonomy requires deliberation – it is about thought-out or deliberated self-rule. Autonomy is not simple choice and choice is not necessarily autonomous.²³

Dignity of the person demands both, that healthcare facility be provided to patients and also that healthcare providers respect the autonomy of the patients.

4. VATICAN II AND THE POOR CHURCH FOR THE POOR

Modern magisterial social teaching on the question of poverty and economic exploitation begins with the encyclical of Pope Leo XIII issued on 15 May 1891. *Rerum Novarum* criticized the condition of the working class and their pathetic situation. For the first time since the beginning of the industrial revolution, the Church intervened in this crucial matter. The Church did this because the faith involves the wellbeing of the whole person. Pope Leo XIII stated that the desire of the Church is that “poor, (...) should rise above poverty and wretchedness, and better their conditions in life” (RN 28). The Pope spoke about the sheer disparity between

²² Raanan Gillon, “Defending the Four Principles approach as a Good Basis for Good Medical Practice and Therefore for Good Medical Ethics,” *Journal of Medical Ethics* 42 (2015): 111-116.

²³ *Ibid.*, 113.

the “enormous fortunes of some few individuals, and the utter poverty of the masses” (RN 1). He discarded the exploitation of the destitute and the indigent as immoral for the sake of gain. The Church presented a balanced social ethical position and rejected extreme ideologies²⁴ that were not in agreement with Catholic teaching. The social teaching of the Church has also criticized the dominance of unbridled liberalism and free market which are not regulated by ethical principles.

Vatican II continued the teaching of *Rerum Novarum* and reiterated it. However, it set new accents, which define today's Church, to be a church of the poor and a church for the poor.²⁵ The Council has been praised for its spirit of renewal of the Church's life. It has redefined the Church of the “margins” in the sense that she is closer and present in the margins of our world.²⁶ The bishops from around the Globe wished to see a serving and poor church rather than a rich and influential one.²⁷ The pastoral constitution *Gaudium et Spes* speaks in its very first lines about the marginality of the Church in today's world. The initial words of the Council's Document address the issue of the anguish and anxieties of the people, especially the poor. “The joys and the hopes, the griefs and the anxieties of the men of this age, especially those who are poor or in any way afflicted, these are the joys and hopes, the griefs and anxieties of the followers of Christ. Indeed, nothing genuinely human fails to raise an echo in their hearts.”²⁸ The Council relives the nature of the Church as the Church of the poor.²⁹ The spirit of Vatican II put poverty at the

²⁴ Rejection of Socialism, *Rerum Novarum*, nos. 4, 38, 48.

²⁵ Gerald S. Twomey, *The “Preferential Option for the Poor” in Catholic Social Thought from John XXIII and John Paul II* (New York: Edwin Mellen Press, 2005).

²⁶ Massimo Faggioli, “Vatican II and the Church of the Margins,” *Theological Studies* 74 (2013): 808-818.

²⁷ Norbert Arntz, *Katakombenpakt: Für eine dienende und Arme Kirche* (Kevelaer: Topos, 2015).

²⁸ *Gaudium et Spes*, no. 1.

²⁹ Raimundo C. Barreto, *Base Ecumenism: Latin American Contributions to Ecumenical Praxis and Theology* (Augsburg: Fortress, Fortress Press, 2025).

core of the Church. She is the Church of all and in particular of the poor. This ecclesial understanding is in consonance with the Pact of the Catacombs and the Latin American context.

5. THE PACT OF THE CATACOMBS: A SERVANT CHURCH

On 16 November 1965, towards the end of the Ecumenical Council, some 40 bishops made their way to an ancient, underground basilica in the catacombs of Domitilla. Their intention was to celebrate the Eucharist and they had their secret agenda. The gathered bishops had the intention to make a common pledge to live the Gospel and follow the call of the Council, a church of the poor. They emphasized the preferential option for the poor, where the Church shares its strength, hope, and life with the poor. The group was led by the Archbishop of Recife in Brazil, Dom Helder Camara.³⁰ The Pact is an invitation to all, especially bishops, to live a life of poverty, to be a church of service and at the side of the powerless.³¹ The Pact of the Catacombs revives and reminds the essentials of our faith and the simplicity of the Gospel. It is based on biblical texts and witness, an ideal for all Christians.

In that night in the Domitilla Catacombs, the signatories of the Pact committed themselves to the following:

[W]e will give whatever is needed in terms of our time, our reflection, our heart, our means, etc., to the apostolic and pastoral service of workers and labour groups and to those who are economically weak and disadvantaged, without allowing that to detract from the welfare of other persons or groups of the diocese. We will support lay people, religious, deacons and priests whom the Lord calls to evangelize the poor and the workers, by sharing their lives and their labours.³²

³⁰ Xabier Pikaza and Jose Antunes Da Silva (eds.), *The Pact of the Catacombs: The Mission of the Poor in the Church* (Spain: Verbo Divino, 2015).

³¹ Hector Scerri, "The Pact of the Catacombs: An Early Harbinger of Pope Francis' Vision of the Church," *Journal of Cultural and Religious Studies* 7 (2019): 325-331.

³² *Ibid.*, 325.

The aspirations of the Pact have not died out, but live further in the hearts and minds of many, who wish to live the spirit of poor Christ.

6. POPE FRANCIS AND HIS MISSION TO THE PERIPHERIES

The pontificate of Pope Francis has highlighted a vision for the Church and her mission in the world that embraces the peripheries as the very fabric of Christian life. It focuses on the neglected, marginalized, and outcasts of the society. Pope Francis clearly showed no inhibition to declare himself as a friend of the underprivileged.³³ He understood himself as one from the periphery of the world. His first words as Pope were, “you know that it was the duty of conclave to give Rome a bishop. It seems that my brother Cardinals have gone to the ends of the earth to get one. ... but here we are.”

Pope Francis has not directly advocated the tenets of the Pact of the Catacombs, but we find several traces in his lifestyle, in his writings and teaching. We recognize the spirit of the Pact in his pontificate:

Pope Francis puts this into practice through his continuous reaching out to the poor, which is inextricably bound to his clear pastoral options and the way he seeks to implement them. The very spirit of the Pact of the Catacombs has emerged strongly in the pastoral style and impetus of Pope Francis.³⁴

The Apostolic Exhortation *Evangelii Gaudium*, “the joy of the Gospel,” Pope Francis’ first major writing, was published eight months after becoming the Pope. It is considered as the manifesto for the new pontificate and a key to understand Francis’ papacy. He supported a church that

³³ Ana Maria Bidegain, “We Finally Have a Pope on the Side of the Poor,” in *Pope Francis and the Search for God in Americas: The Significance of His Early Visits to the Americas*, ed. Maria. C. Bingemer and Peter J. Casarella (Catholic University of America Press, 2021), 72-93.

³⁴ Scerri, “The Pact of the Catacombs,” 330.

is “bruised, hurting and dirty because it has been out on the streets.”³⁵ It called upon the Church to step out of her comfort zone and to shine in the darkest areas of human existence. He understood the Church and its mission in a very Franciscan spirit.³⁶ He invited the faithful in the following words:

In our day Jesus’ command to “go and make disciples” echoes in the changing scenarios and ever new challenges to the Church’s mission of evangelization [...]. Each Christian and every community must discern the path that the Lord points out, but all of us are asked to obey his call to go forth from our own comfort zone in order to reach all the “peripheries” in need of the light of the Gospel.³⁷

From the very first moments of his papacy, Pope Francis showed deep concern for the sick, poor, and vulnerable. Without this background, we cannot understand his teaching and his dedication. In his homily, read by Msgr. Rino Fisichella on the occasion of the Jubilee of the sick and the Health Care Workers just few weeks before his death, Pope Francis addressed doctors and medical staff.

Dear doctors, nurses and health care workers, in caring for your patients, especially the most vulnerable among them, the Lord constantly affords you an opportunity to renew your lives through gratitude, mercy, and hope (cf. *Spes Non confundit*, 11). He calls you to realize with humility that nothing in life is to be taken for granted and that everything is a gift from God; to enrich your lives with the sense of humanity we experience when, beyond appearances, only the things that matter remain: the small and great signs of love. Allow the presence of the sick to enter your lives as a gift, to heal your hearts, to purify them of all that is not charity, and to warm them with the ardent and gentle fire of compassion.³⁸

³⁵ Pope Francis, *Apostolic Exhortation “Evangelii Gaudium,”* Rome 2013, no. 49.

³⁶ Stephan Winter, “[...] from our own Comfort Zone (...) to [...] -All the Peripheries’ (EG 20): A Franciscan Keyword of Pope Francis and its Significance for Christian Worship,” *Religion* 9 (2018): 290.

³⁷ *Evangelii Gaudium*, no. 20.

³⁸ Homily on 5th Sunday in Lent, 6 April 2025, <https://www.vatican.va/content/>

Reflecting on his own health struggles, he accentuated the need for a healthcare system that prioritizes the poor and vulnerable of the world. Pope Francis often stated that healthcare is a fundamental right of all people and not a privilege of the rich. Healthcare should not be a question of economic status, but of global equality in health services. Todd A. Salzman and Michael G. Lawler have critically appraised the Ethical and Religious Directives for Catholic Health Care Service (ERD) of the United States Conference of Catholic Bishops (USCCB). The Authors analyze the shortcomings of the revised version and point out that this fails to incorporate Pope Francis' theological understanding and pastoral priorities.

Francis has fundamentally transformed catholic anthropology, ecclesiology, and ethical methodology, yet there is no evidence of this transformation in the revised ERD. We are guided by the transformative impact of Francis's papacy throughout the commentary and demonstrate how it should impact future revisions of ERD in particular and catholic health ethics in general.³⁹

Pope Francis called the Christians to live the Gospel with radical solidarity with the poor. The Catholic social principles of human dignity, solidarity, and subsidiarity should help everyone to have access to suitable healthcare. The Pope has often called upon world leaders not to neglect social justice, especially towards the poor and the sick.

7. VATICAN II & THE LATIN AMERICAN CHURCH

The Second Vatican Council gave a strong impetus for the renewal of the faith and the life of the Church. The Council provided for the Latin American Church "the catalyst for the

francesco/en/homilies/2025/documents/20250406-omelia-giubileo-ammalati.html (accessed on 20.05.2025).

³⁹ Todd A. Salzman and Michael G. Lawler, *Pope Francis and the Transformation of Health Care Ethics* (Washington DC: Georgetown University Press, 2021), ii.

development of a truly autochthonous Church.”⁴⁰ However, Latin American Church was not a subject in the deliberations of the Council. European bishops and theologians led the theological and pastoral discussions during the meetings, and “very little if anything referring directly to Latin America found its way into the final document of the Council.”⁴¹ Nonetheless, the Latin American Church and its Episcopate have reflected over the theological impulses for the Church in South America. The bishops came together to begin the process of reception in Medellin (1968), Puebla (1979), Santo Domingo (1992), and in Aparecida (2007).⁴²

The concentration on the existential peripheries of our Church and the world has a longer history and pastoral basis. The Fifth General Latin American Bishops’ Conference and the Caribbean (CELAM) took place in Aparecida in 2007, where the Archbishop of Buenos Aires, Jorge Cardinal Bergoglio was the President of the conference.⁴³ The conference unequivocally reaffirmed its commitment and mission “the preferential option for the poor.”⁴⁴ The Aparecida Document is the fruit of deep reflection on the relevant issues related to the life and faith of the continent, and mentions some of them.⁴⁵ The bishops reflected over

⁴⁰ O. Ernesto Valiente, “The Reception of Vatican II in Latin American,” *Theological Studies* 73 (2012): 795.

⁴¹ Enrique Dussel, “Latin America,” in *Modern Catholicism: Vatican II and After*, ed. Adrian Hastings (New York: Oxford University Press, 1991), 319.

⁴² *Ibid.*, 801-822.

⁴³ Jorge Mario Bergoglio, *The Aparecida Document, CreateSpace Independent Platform*, 2013.

⁴⁴ The Aparecida Conference from 11-31 May 2007 on the theme: Disciples and Missionaries of Jesus Christ so that our peoples may have life in Him. “I am the Way, the Truth and the Life” (Jn 14:6). This document contains numerous indications rich pastoral reflections in the light of faith and the current social context. Cf. <https://www.ltr.arizona.edu/~katie/kt/misc/Apercida/Aparecida-document-for-printing.pdf> (accessed on 20.05.2025).

⁴⁵ To keep the Gospel Message alive and relevant in the life of the people; Helping Christians to have a personal and authentic encounter with Christ; Living with simplicity and humility as taught in the Gospel; serious concern for the wellbeing of Mother Earth and fostering a life of prayer especially popular cultural devotions.

globalization, discipleship, mission, structural sin, and the future of the Church in Latin America.⁴⁶ The Apostolic Exhortation *Evangelii Gaudium* has integrated main themes from the Aparecida document. The spirit of Aparecida is promoted in *Evangelii Gaudium*. Pope Francis brought the main theological themes from *Evangelii Nuntiandi* and Aparecida together.

8. “PREFERENTIAL OPTION FOR THE POOR” OR “COMPASSION FOR THE VULNERABLE”

Michel Temgo asks in his book, if the “preferential option for the poor” was enjoying its new springtime in the days of Pope Francis? He analyzes the concept of preferential option for the poor in the context of the liberation theology of Latin America in the writings of the liberation theologian Jon Sobrino⁴⁷ and from Pope Francis. In the context of the liberation theology, the concept of the poor is mainly applied to human vulnerability. They are the socio-economic poor or victims of political injustice, who are exploited, oppressed, and theologically “crucified people.” Pope Francis spoke not only about socio-economic poor, but also about spiritual poor, especially those “exposed to the possibility of being hurt or weakened.”⁴⁸ He espoused vulnerability in relation to the economic and consumerist society.⁴⁹ For him, poor are those who are suffering from racial discrimination, LGBTQI Groups, or victims of climate changes. Michel Temgo considers that the biblical concept of the preferential option for the poor cannot be replaced with another biblical concept of compassion for the vulnerable.⁵⁰ Pope Francis used an

⁴⁶ Robert S. Pelton (ed.), *Aparecida: Quo Vadis?* (Scranton: University of Scranton Press, 2008).

⁴⁷ A Spanish Jesuit (born 1938) who has made great contributions to the Latin American liberation theology.

⁴⁸ Michel Simo Temgo, *Jon Sobrino and Pope Francis: A New Springtime for the Preferential Option for the Poor/Vulnerable* (Bloomington, IN: Xlibris, 2018), 19.

⁴⁹ *Ibid.*, 284.

⁵⁰ *Ibid.*, 293-296.

integral concept to understand poor, which is inclusive of all categories of human sufferings and hardships.

Pope Francis was the bishop in Argentina during the turbulent decades of 1970's and 80's of the military dictatorship. Having the firsthand experience of the struggles of the poor, he continued to show his concern for the poor and their wellbeing as pope.⁵¹ He conscientized the Christians and the Church itself to seek out and assist those on the peripheries of human societies (cf. EG 20).

In the first ever papal encyclical on Environment, *Laudato Si'*, Pope Francis approached every person living on the Earth and shared his ardent concern and care for the state of the Mother Earth. He entered into dialogue with all persons. He associated two central issues of humankind which are endangered today. It is the cry of the mother earth and the cry of the poor. This striking word "the cry of the earth, and the cry of the poor"⁵² is borrowed from the liberation theology from South American context. The former Brazilian priest and liberation theologian Leonardo Boff (*1938) used this phrase to show the linkage between the suffering of the underprivileged and the untrammelled exploitation of the natural world, which exacerbated social injustice.⁵³ The encyclical analyzed six influential concepts, which help to understand the background for the ecological crisis.⁵⁴ Pope Francis expounded the authentic interpretation

⁵¹ Cathleen Kaveny, "Pope Francis and Catholic Health Care Ethics," *Theological Studies* 80 (2019): 186-201.

⁵² Pope Francis, *Encyclical Letter Laudato Si'. On Care for our Common Home*, Rome 2015, no. 49.

⁵³ Leonardo Boff, *Cry of the Earth, and Cry of the Poor*, trans. Phillip Berrymann, Ecology and Justice Series. (Maryknoll, NY: Orbis Books, 1997). Boff had written the book in 1995 in Portuguese language. Latin American Liberation Theology recognized the connection between the ecological destruction and the social injustice that were helped structures to perpetuate them.

⁵⁴ They are integral ecology (nos. 137-162), intergenerational solidarity (nos. 159-162), technocratic paradigm (nos. 106-114), tyrannical anthropocentrism (nos. 115-121), ecological conversion (nos. 216-221), and the willingness to hear the cry of the Earth and the cry of the poor (no. 49).

of the biblical words (Gen 1:18; 2:15), and its consequences for Christian faith and environmental responsibility.⁵⁵

The Pope exhorted the humanity to respect the earth and stop exploiting and hurting the planet – the home for all creation. His emotional appeal is a request to feel with the sister earth:

This sister now cries out to us because of the harm we have inflicted on her by our irresponsible use and abuse of the goods with which God has endowed her. We have come to see ourselves as her lords and masters, entitled to plunder her at will. The violence present in our hearts, wounded by sin, is also reflected in the symptoms of sickness evident in the soil, in the water, in the air and in all forms of life.⁵⁶

An integral ecology includes the principle of common good. Pope Francis defined the concept of common good in the encyclical as “the sum of those conditions of social life which allow social groups and their individual members relatively thorough and ready access to their own fulfilment.”⁵⁷ Persons and human life are treated like objects in this throwaway culture. The concept of throwaway culture was a significant concept in Pope Francis’ Catholic Social Teaching.⁵⁸ He urged the Christians to follow a culture of encounter and of hospitality.⁵⁹ A throwaway culture-mentality is increasingly prevalent in our world today. We have rejected and suppressed some social groups for whatsoever reasons and treated them as undesired, which is ethically unacceptable.

CONCLUSION

Healthcare ethics is a branch of applied ethics that is concerned with various moral decision-making situations in

⁵⁵ Thomas Massaro, “What Precisely Did Pope Francis Contribute? Parsing Key Terms and Claims in *Laudato Si*,” *Social Sciences* 12 (2023): 552.

⁵⁶ *Laudato Si*, no. 2.

⁵⁷ *Laudato Si*, no. 156.

⁵⁸ Jeffrey W. Fuchs and Joseph R. Fuchs, “Counteracting Throwaway Culture in Daily Clinical Practice,” *The Linacre Quarterly* 88 (2020): 65-70.

⁵⁹ Charles C. Comosy, *Resisting Throwaway Culture: How a Consistent Life Ethic can Unite a Fractured People* (New York: New City Press, 2019), 23-24.

the field of medicine. Advancement in medical knowledge and technologies have not only brought hope and healing to many people suffering from life-threatening illnesses, but it has also raised many moral questions. Nothing is more desirable to human welfare and wellbeing as one's health. We must be concerned about the health of all human beings, independent of their socio-economic or cultural conditions.

Poverty and ill-health are interconnected; they influence each other reciprocally. Economic poverty is a major cause of ailments, and it determines the access to healthcare. The poor and outcasts are not in a situation to afford facilities needed for maintaining good health, including healthy nourishment.⁶⁰ Unfortunately, the poor do not get sufficient space in the ethical discourse. Through his constant reminders, Pope Francis has strengthened the awareness for the poor and developed a theology of the poor. This theology calls upon Christians to fight for social justice for the poor and downtrodden, and to serve as advocates for those who have no voice.

The sense of justice and equality is not common in many cultures of the world. Many socio-economic and political criteria have taken the place of determining, who gets medical treatment and who are excluded. There are groups of people in all societies who are susceptible to abuse and neglect. The fundamental principles of universal health ethics are respect for every person, beneficence, justice, utility, and solidarity. These basic values are essential to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). At the same time, no amount of legal and international declarations can provide the guarantee for healthcare to the poor. Jesus mitigated the sufferings of the needy and helpless. He was extremely sensitive to their needs. So too Pope Francis identified himself with the needy, homeless, and the sick.

⁶⁰ Owen O' Donnell, "Health and health system effects on poverty: A narrative review of Global evidence," *Health Policy* 142/3 (2024).

He gave a face to the faceless, bringing them inner healing and joy. Poverty has many faces and realms. Pope Francis stated that “we are called to find Christ in them, to lend our voice to their causes, but also to be their friends, to listen to them, to speak for them and to embrace the mysterious wisdom which God wishes to share with us through them” (EG 198). He lived a life of full adherence to the Gospel and fully lived the word in Tob 4:7: “Do not turn your face away from anyone who is poor.”

Excerpts taken from Aloysius Pieris SJ, *God's Reign for God's Poor: A Return to the Jesus Formula*, second edition; Gonawala-Kelaniya, Sri Lanka: Tulana Research Centre, 1998.

“My resources or ‘riches’ (time, money, competence, influence) acquire their salvific value only when they are expended for my poor neighbour. Unless shared with the victims of exploitation, such resources become Mammon, a source of my enmity with God. I become myself an exploiter and forfeit my salvation, being responsible for my neighbour’s death.”

“Those who seek doctrinal precision by forging a formulatory theology today accuse the Asians of turning theology into poetry. We insist that the language of poetry, drama and parable will always remain the language that will provoke action. Mere dogmatic formulae, in themselves, tend to intoxicate the intellect with a narcissistic indulgence in speculations. It is gnosis without agape, knowledge without action.